

INTEGRALLARNING RATSIONAL QISMINI AJRATISHDA OSTROGRADSKIY USULI

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Аннотация. Ushbu maqola Ostrogradskiy usulidan foydalanib ratsional funksiyalarni integallash haqida bo'lib, ushbu usul yordamida misol yechib ko'rsatilgan.

Калит со'zlar: Ko'phad, sodda kasr, ratsional funksiya, differentsiallashtirish, integrallashtirish, Ostrogradskiy usuli

Annotation. This article is about the integration of rational functions using the Ostrogradsky method, with an example solution using this method.

Keywords: Polynomial, simple fraction, rational function, differentiation, integration, Ostrogradsky method

Ratsional kasrlarni sodda kasrlarga yoyib integrallashtirishda ko'p hollarda, murakkab hisoblashlar bajarishga to'g'ri keladi. Ba'zi hollarda, integral ostidagi ratsional kasrning shaklini almashtirib, o'zgaruvchilarni almashtirish, bo'laklab integrallashtirish usullaridan foydalanish, berilgan integralni hisoblashni yengillashtiradi.

Quyidagi $\frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}$ to'g'ri kasrning maxraji kompleks ildizlarga ega bo'lganda, uni integrallashtirishda, murakkab hisoblashlar bajarishga to'g'ri keladi.

Bunday hollarda ushbu

$$\int \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} dx = \frac{P_1(x)}{Q_1(x)} + \int \frac{P_2(x)}{Q_2(x)} dx \quad (1)$$

Ostrogradskiy formulasidan foydalanish qulay bo'ladi, bunda $Q_2(x)$ -ildizlari $Q(x)$ ko'phadning hamma sodda (bir karrali) ildizlaridan iborat bo'lgan ko'phad, $Q(x) = Q_1(x) \cdot Q_2(x)$, bu yerda $P(x) = n$, $Q(x) = m$, $Q_2(x) = p$, $Q_1(x) = m - p$ darajali ko'phadlar $P_1(x)$ va $P_2(x)$ ($P_1(x) = A_s x^s + \dots + A_1 x + A_0$, $P_2(x) = B_r x^r + \dots + B_1 x + B_0$, $s = n - p + 1$ va $r = n + p - m$) lar noma'lum koeffitsientli ko'phadlar bo'lib,

$\frac{P_1(x)}{Q_1(x)}$ va $\frac{P_2(x)}{Q_2(x)}$ - to'g'ri kasrlardan iborat.

$P_1(x)$ va $P_2(x)$ ko'phadlarni topish uchun ularni noma'lum koeffitsientlar yordamida yozib olib, so'ngra (1) ning ikkala tomonini differentsiallaymiz, natijada, (1) tenglikka teng kuchli,

$$\frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} = \left(\frac{P_1(x)}{Q_1(x)} \right)' + \frac{P_2(x)}{Q_2(x)} \quad (2)$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz. Bu tenglikdan noma‘lum koeffitsientlar usulidan foydalanib, $P_1(x)$ va $P_2(x)$ larning tarkibidagi noma‘lum koeffitsientlarni topamiz. Ostrogradskiy formulasi, integralning ratsional qismini integrallasdan ajratishga imkon berdi, $\frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}$ to‘g‘ri kasrni integrallash masalasi, unga nisbatan osonroq integrallanadigan

$\frac{P_2(x)}{Q_2(x)}$ to‘g‘ri kasrni integrallashga keltiriladi.

Misol $\int \frac{x^4 + x^3 + x + 4}{(x^3 + 1)^2} dx$ integralni Ostrogradskiy usulida yordamida hisoblang.

$$\left[\int \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} dx = \frac{P_1(x)}{Q_1(x)} + \int \frac{P_2(x)}{Q_2(x)} dx \right]$$

$$\begin{cases} Q(x) = (x^3 + 1)^2 \\ Q'(x) = 2(x^3 + 1) \cdot 3x^2 \end{cases}$$

$$Q(x), Q'(x), Q_1(x) = x^3 + 1, Q_2(x) = \frac{Q(x)}{Q_1(x)}, Q_2(x) = x^3 + 1$$

$$P_1(x) = Ax^2 + Bx + C, P_2(x) = Dx^2 + Ex + F$$

$$\int \frac{x^4 + x^3 + x + 4}{(x^3 + 1)^2} dx = \frac{Ax^2 + Bx + C}{x^3 + 1} + \int \frac{Dx^2 + Ex + F}{x^3 + 1} dx$$

tenglikni ikkala tomonini differensiallaymiz:

$$\left(\int \frac{x^4 + x^3 + x + 4}{(x^3 + 1)^2} dx \right)' = \left(\frac{Ax^2 + Bx + C}{x^3 + 1} \right)' + \left(\int \frac{Dx^2 + Ex + F}{x^3 + 1} dx \right)'$$

$$\frac{x^4 + x^3 + x + 4}{(x^3 + 1)^2} = \frac{(2Ax + B)(x^3 + 1) - (Ax^2 + Bx + C) \cdot 3x^2}{(x^3 + 1)^2} + \frac{(Dx^2 + Ex + F)(x^3 + 1)}{(x^3 + 1)^2}$$

ayniyatda maxrajlarini tashlab suratlarini tenglashtiramiz

$$x^4 + x^3 + x + 4 = (2Ax + B)(x^3 + 1) - (Ax^2 + Bx + C) \cdot 3x^2 + (Dx^2 + Ex + F)(x^3 + 1)$$

$$x^4 + x^3 + x + 4 =$$

$$= 2Ax^4 + 2Ax + Bx^3 + B - 3Ax^4 - 3Bx^3 - 3Cx^2 + Dx^5 + Dx^2 + Ex^4 + Ex + Fx^3 + F$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 x^5 \\
 x^4 \\
 x^3 \\
 x^2 \\
 x \\
 x^0
 \end{array}
 \left| \begin{array}{l}
 D = 0 \\
 2A - 3A + E = 1 \\
 B - 3B + F = 1 \\
 -3C + D = 0 \\
 2A + E = 1 \\
 B + F = 4
 \end{array} \right.
 \Rightarrow
 \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 D = 0, \\
 -A + E = 1, \quad (1) \\
 -2B + F = 1, \quad (2) \\
 C = 0, \quad (3) \\
 2A + E = 1, \quad (4) \\
 B + F = 4, \quad (5)
 \end{array} \right.$$

Topilgan koeffisientlarni noma'lumlar o'rniga qo'yib quyidagi ifodani hosil qilamiz.

$$\int \frac{x^4 + x^3 + x + 4}{(x^3 + 1)^2} dx = \frac{x}{x^3 + 1} + \int \frac{x + 3}{x^3 + 1} dx$$

$I_1 = \int \frac{x + 3}{x^3 + 1} dx = \int \frac{x + 3}{(x + 1)(x^2 - x + 1)} dx$ ni alohida belgilab olib ratsional ifodani

integrallaymiz, integral ostidagi ifodani sodda kasrlarga ajratamiz.

$$\frac{x + 3}{(x + 1)(x^2 - x + 1)} = \frac{M}{x + 1} + \frac{Nx + P}{x^2 - x + 1} = \frac{M(x^2 - x + 1) + (Nx + P)(x + 1)}{(x + 1)(x^2 - x + 1)}$$

$$x + 3 = M(x^2 - x + 1) + (Nx + P)(x + 1)$$

$$x + 3 = Mx^2 - Mx + M + Nx^2 + Nx + Px + P$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 x^2 \\
 x \\
 x^0
 \end{array}
 \left| \begin{array}{l}
 M + N = 0 \quad (1) \\
 -M + N + P = 1 \quad (2) \\
 M + P = 3 \quad (3)
 \end{array} \right.
 \Rightarrow
 (1, 2) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 N = -M \\
 P = 3 - M
 \end{array} \right.
 \Rightarrow
 \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 -M - M + 3 - M = 1 \\
 \Rightarrow
 \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 M = \frac{2}{3} \\
 N = -\frac{2}{3} \\
 P = \frac{7}{3}
 \end{array} \right.$$

Topilgan koeffisientlardan foydalanib integralni yozamiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 &= \int \frac{x + 3}{(x + 1)(x^2 - x + 1)} dx = \int \left(\frac{M}{x + 1} + \frac{Nx + P}{x^2 - x + 1} \right) dx = \int \left(\frac{\frac{2}{3}}{x + 1} + \frac{-\frac{2}{3}x + \frac{7}{3}}{x^2 - x + 1} \right) dx = \\
 &= \frac{2}{3} \int \frac{dx}{x + 1} - \frac{1}{3} \int \frac{2x - 7}{x^2 - x + 1} dx = \frac{2}{3} \int \frac{dx}{x + 1} - \frac{1}{3} \int \frac{2x - 1 - 6}{x^2 - x + 1} dx = \frac{2}{3} \int \frac{dx}{x + 1} - \frac{1}{3} \int \frac{2x - 1}{x^2 - x + 1} dx + \\
 &+ 2 \int \frac{d\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)}{\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\right)^2} = \frac{2}{3} \int \frac{dx}{x + 1} - \frac{1}{3} \int \frac{d(x^2 - x + 1)}{x^2 - x + 1} + 2 \int \frac{d\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)}{\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\right)^2} =
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{2}{3} \ln|x+1| - \frac{1}{3} \ln|x^2 - x + 1| + \frac{4\sqrt{3}}{3} \operatorname{arctg}\left(\frac{2x-1}{\sqrt{3}}\right).$$

Yuqoridagilarni birlashtirib quyidagini hosil qilamiz.

$$\int \frac{x^4 + x^3 + x + 4}{(x^3 + 1)^2} dx =$$

$$= \frac{x}{x^3 + 1} + I_1 = \frac{x}{x^3 + 1} + \frac{2}{3} \ln|x+1| - \frac{1}{3} \ln|x^2 - x + 1| + \frac{4\sqrt{3}}{3} \operatorname{arctg}\left(\frac{2x-1}{\sqrt{3}}\right) + C.$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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